

Raman Spectra Search

Web app usage examples

(visual guide ver.01, 2024-11-09)

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General information

The web application is available from the following address:

<https://spectra.adma.ai/search/>

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Web app main view

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `https://spectra.adma.ai/search/`. The page title is "Raman spectra search". A red banner at the top right of the page content says "The Raman Spectra Search App is under development right now".

The main interface is divided into two main sections:

- Tool box area with search functions:** A vertical sidebar on the left containing six search options, each with a right-pointing chevron:
 - Search by Spectrum File
 - Search by Sample
 - Search by Data provider
 - Search by Dataset
 - Search by Instrument
 - Search by Wavelength
- Search result area:** The main content area on the right, which is currently empty. It contains a "Pages" section and a "Select Spectrum" section. The "Select Spectrum" section displays two identical Raman spectra plots side-by-side. Each plot has a y-axis and an x-axis labeled "wavenumber [cm⁻¹]" with tick marks at 0, 1000, 2000, and 3000. Below each plot is a light blue button labeled "sCal".

Red annotations highlight the "Tool box area with search functions" and the "Search result area".

Web app main view

**Hide/Show Tool box pane
In order to use entire screen
for spectra visualization**

Web app main view

Raman spectra search

spectra.adma.ai/search/

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Raman spectra search

- Search by Spectrum File
- Search by Sample
- Search by Data provider
- Search by Dataset
- Search by Instrument
- Search by Wavelength

Pages

0

Select Spectrum

Numbers of Hits

10

wavenumber [cm⁻¹]

sCal

sCal

sCal

Select/adjust the number of hitlist spectra to be visualized on a single page

Scrolling

Scroll up/down to inspect entire search result (hit list)

Spectra selection

The image displays a web interface for Raman spectra search. The top part shows a grid of search results, each with a small Raman spectrum plot and the label 'sCal'. One of these plots is highlighted with a red rounded rectangle. A red arrow points from this highlighted plot to a larger, detailed view of the spectrum below. The detailed view shows the Raman shift (cm⁻¹) on the x-axis (0 to 3000) and Raw Counts on the y-axis (0.000 to 0.045). The spectrum shows several peaks, with the most prominent one at approximately 1050 cm⁻¹. A red double-headed arrow on the right side of the detailed view indicates that the user can scroll down to see more of the spectrum.

Upon a spectrum selection detailed spectrum curve is visualized at the bottom of the page

Scroll down to see the spectrum

Hide/show spectra hitlist

Spectra details

Spectra search with an user defined target spectrum

Load a target spectrum from file

The file name and the target spectrum are visualized on top

Search by Spectrum File

FILE NAME

PST02_iRPlus532_Z020_100_550msx5.txt

Choose a File

Text search Spectrum search

Search result - the hitlist spectra similar to the target are show below

Pages

Select Spectrum

Similarity coefficients of the hitlist spectra. The default similarity metrics is cosine

Search (filter) by sample

Select/expand "Search by Sample"

Click with the mouse and a list of all available samples in the database are shown. If needed, type a text to pre-filter the list.

Search for Samples

R040070
Neon
SOB
sCal
PST
R040029
R040137

Scroll down and select the target sample and explore the search result.

Two Raman spectra plots are shown, each with a prominent peak at approximately 1000 cm⁻¹. The x-axis is labeled "wavenumber [cm⁻¹]" and ranges from 0 to 3000. Below each plot is a button labeled "sCal".

Search (filter) by sample

Now the shown results contain spectra with sample “PST”

Instrument type, investigation project, provider and, in this case, the laser wave length are shown

Search (filter) by Data provider

Select/expand “Search by Data provider”

Scroll down and select the provider of interest.

The filtered results are shown automatically

The screenshot shows a search interface with a sidebar on the left and a main content area. The sidebar has a search bar and several search methods: 'Search by Spectrum file', 'Search by Sample', 'Search by Data provider' (highlighted with a red box), 'Search for Providers' (with a search input), 'Search by Dataset', and 'Search by Instrument'. Under 'Search by Data provider', a list of providers is shown: 'CSIC-ICV', 'NTUA', 'ICV_CSIC' (highlighted with a red box), 'TOPCOF', 'Elodiz', 'LBF', and 'CSIC-ICP'. The main content area displays a grid of 10 infrared spectra plots, each with a wavenumber axis from 0 to 3000 cm⁻¹. The plots are arranged in two rows of five. The first row shows spectra for 'sCal' (three plots) and 'Neon' (two plots). The second row shows spectra for 'Neon' (three plots) and 'PST' (one plot). A red arrow points from the 'ICV_CSIC' provider in the sidebar to the first plot in the second row. At the bottom right, there is a red text label 'No image selected'.

Search (filter) by Dataset

Select/expand
"Search by Dataset"

Scroll down and select the dataset of
interest.
The filtered results are shown
automatically

The screenshot shows a web application for searching Raman spectra. On the left, a sidebar contains search options: "Search by Sample", "Search by Data provider", "Search by Dataset" (highlighted with a red box and a red arrow), "Search by Instrument", and "Search by Wavelength". Below these is a search input field labeled "Search for Dataset". Underneath, a list of datasets is shown under the heading "All Dataset". One dataset, "10.1038/s41597-022-01883-5", is highlighted with a red box and a red arrow pointing to the right. The main area of the page displays a grid of Raman spectra plots, each with a title below it. The titles include "ABS PLAS193", "algin BIOL006", "beachcast white foam sheet PLAS251", "blue fragment PLAS253", "bone BIOL001", "bone BIOL007", "bone BIOL009", "bone BIOL025", "BPF PLAS233", and "BR PLAS226". Each plot shows intensity versus wavenumber in cm⁻¹, with the x-axis ranging from 0 to 3000. The interface also shows browser tabs and a search bar at the top.

Search (filter) by Instrument

Select/expand "Search by Instrument"

Scroll down and select the instrument. The filtered results are shown automatically

The screenshot displays a web application interface for searching Raman spectra. On the left, a sidebar contains several search methods: "Search by Spectrum File", "Search by Sample", "Search by Data provider", "Search by Dataset", and "Search by Instrument". The "Search by Instrument" option is highlighted with a red box and a red arrow pointing to it. Below this sidebar is a search input field labeled "Search for Instruments" and a list of instrument names: "Horiba_nan", "Renishaw InVia Reflex", "Renishaw_InVia Reflex", "Zolix FinderEdge", "Elodiz_EZI860", and "Elodiz_ZLM896". The "Elodiz_EZI860" option is also highlighted with a red box and a red arrow pointing to it. The main content area, titled "Select Spectrum", shows a grid of 10 Raman spectra plots. Each plot has an x-axis labeled "wavenumber [cm⁻¹]" ranging from 0 to 3000. The plots are arranged in two rows of five. The first row shows five spectra with prominent peaks at approximately 1000 and 1500 cm⁻¹. The second row shows five spectra, with the first one being a flat line and the others showing similar peak patterns to the first row. Each plot is labeled "sCal" below it.

Search (filter) by wavelength

Select/expand "Search by wavelength"

Scroll down and select the wavelength. The filtered results are shown automatically

The screenshot displays a search interface for Raman spectra. On the left, a sidebar contains search filters: "Search by Data provider", "Search by Dataset", "Search by Instrument", and "Search by Wavelength". The "Search by Wavelength" option is highlighted with a red box. Below it is a search input field labeled "Search for Wavelengths" and a list of "All Wavelengths" including 785, 552, and 633. The 785 cm⁻¹ option is also highlighted with a red box. A red arrow points from the "Search by Wavelength" filter to the 785 cm⁻¹ selection. Another red arrow points from the 785 cm⁻¹ selection to the search results. The search results are a 2x3 grid of plots. The top row shows three identical plots with multiple peaks, each labeled "sCal" below it. The middle row shows the first two plots with the same multiple peaks, but the third plot is a flat line, also labeled "sCal". The bottom row shows three plots, each with a single prominent peak at 785 cm⁻¹, labeled "sCal". The x-axis for all plots is "wavenumber [cm⁻¹]" ranging from 0 to 3000.